

THE ROLE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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Technology is one of the crucial factors of developing both teaching and learning processes in educational settings, mainly for the English language teaching. This may contribute the teacher to present a masterful lesson to students. Technology is very important for the field of education since there can be too many things which the teachers are able to do, such as playing videos in English language or a song, movie and even a theatre show.

Technology, mainly laptops and computers have made a vast difference in our society, as well as on the field of teaching English. Many years ago there were not very many forms of technology that existed. People often used type writes or played board games for entertainment. However, nowadays, the use of laptops has become extremely popular. If an individual is not using a computer for some form of entertainment, they are most likely using it

ABSTRACT

This article highlights the importance of information technology during conducting English lessons and gives some practical examples of its usage.

for something along the lines of school or work.

Many universities, in an effort to increase their effectiveness and efficiency in order to develop competitive advantages in their educational setting, are usually eager to improve information technology on their teaching systems. The age of information technology provides possibilities for an effective coordination of teaching process. Different educational centers and universities transact electronically in the modern teaching environment and this creates a push factor for designing lesson plans on the existence of technological gadgets. Meanwhile, teaching English through the help of technology may also reduce the waste of paper during classes. Therefore, I would like to add some pros and cons to the paperless office as an example of benefits of having electronic documents. In my

personal view, there are enough advantages to have a paperless office. For example, companies may be able to greatly reduce the amount of paper that they use. Not only does this contribute the environment, but also it may help cut costs within the organization. Secondly, companies may also be able to improve service through implementing the paperless office. This is because communication is immediate and does not get lost in a pile of papers on someone's desk. Moreover, a paperless office can also save money of the company.

On the other hand, there also some disadvantages in having a paperless office: it may straightly refer to the issue security. As a result there is a question: how does a company make sure that only the eyes the document is intended for, are the only eyes that see it? Also how does a company know an electronic communication is authentic? The other critical problem is privacy. There is also peculiar question: how does a company make sure that when an electronic communication is sent only the person it is intended for will read it? The answers for these disadvantages lie on the question itself.

The use of new modern technology gives learners to have a natural context for learner autonomy, context for the identity of learner, some possible ways of language usage, and inspiration for students to make new collaborative and interational chances between teachers and students under these forms (Murray, 2005) [1]. Technology plays a crucial role in promoting learners' activities and owns a substantial impact on teaching approaches. If teachers do not utilize technology in

teaching, they cannot keep up with the latest advanced technology. Therefore, they are required to have complete expertise in teaching language skills in these technologies (Pourhosein Gilakjani, 2017; Solanki & Shyamlee, 2012) [3], [4]. Potential technological methods which might play an important role in teaching, mainly in speaking and listening are also provided by Nomass. According to him it is clear that English language learners are able to acquire a foreign language easily, due to the use of web-based language learning programs, innovative presentations software, dictionaries, chat functions and emails, and computer-assisted language learning programs. The very research has been carried out in the case study tradition and focused on the utilization of technology at universities to master the English language by a group of students. Nomass mentions the current technology issues in classrooms in his recommendations for future research and how these could be taken into consideration. The problems include the division in the modern classroom between theory and practice. He called for technology integration into the language learning practice at these educational places and stated that teachers should take these kinds of innovations into account as well (Nomass, 2013) [2].

In conclusion, conducting English lessons with the help of IT may have a great impact on improving youngsters' knowledge during educational period. Technology plays an important role in today's educational settings, such as universities, schools and colleges.

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